

Did We Create Brave Spaces? A study protocol of a realist evaluation project in health professions education faculty development

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Patient and General Public Involvement Statement:

Trained actors, who are recruited from the general public, take part in simulation during the CBS workshops. Their experience is captured during the focus groups.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST STATEMENTS

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Sonaina Chopra	Sonaina Chopra is a Research Assistant for Research Innovation and Theory (MERIT) program at McMaster University. Ms. Chopra is a collaborator of the MERIT Scholar Research Pilot Grant for a future program evaluation project of the CBS curriculum.
Hannah Jordan	Hannah Jordan is the Standardized Patient Trainer/Coordinator for McMaster University's Waterloo Regional Campus. Ms. Jordan is a collaborator of the MERIT Scholar Research Pilot Grant for a future program evaluation project of the CBS curriculum.
Matt Sibbald	Dr Sibbald is associate professor at McMaster University and receives stipends from McMaster University for various roles in medical education. Dr. Sibbald is a collaborator of the MERIT Scholar Research Pilot Grant for a future program evaluation project of the CBS curriculum.
Aaron Geekie-Sousa	Aaron Geekie-Sousa is the Program Manager for McMaster University's Midwifery Graduate Program.
Sandra Monteiro	Dr. Monteiro is associate professor at McMaster University, and receives salary support from the Faculty of Health Sciences, Department of Medicine. Dr. Monteiro is currently funded by the Medical Council of Canada to conduct an investigation of online exam test security and fairness. Dr. Monteiro is the senior author on the MERIT Scholar Research Pilot Grant for a future program evaluation project of the CBS curriculum.

ABSTRACT

introduction

Microaggressions occur regularly in clinical teaching environments, and are harmful to individuals, teams, and institutions. We conceptualized and piloted a workshop series to train health professions education faculty and staff in disarming microaggressions using a simulation-based education design. Here we describe a realist evaluation study protocol that is in progress, aimed at understanding the context, mechanism and outcomes of this curricular intervention.

methods and analysis

In 2021, a group of faculty and staff volunteers formed the Creating Brave Spaces (CBS) team and designed an innovative faculty development activity to address faculty learning needs in equity, diversity, inclusivity and Indigenous reconciliation. The study team recruited and trained standardized actors who portrayed microaggressions. After an introductory lecture on the definitions and harmful effects of microaggressions, participants practiced disarming microaggressions in a simulated environment. Workshops were presented at faculty development events, faculty retreats, and national and international conferences. From each workshop, the team gained insight and experience that they incorporated into additional deliveries. Starting in 2022, participants were invited to volunteer for a semi-structured interview to discuss their experiences with the workshop. The interviews led participants through a conversation about their professional and personal context, their recollections of the workshop experience, and the impact of the workshop on their attitude and practice. The recordings were transcribed and are being analyzed using thematic analysis with a realist evaluation framework.

ethics and dissemination

The study proposal was reviewed by the Hamilton Integrated Research Ethics Board and was determined to fall within quality improvement/program evaluation, and as such was granted a waiver from a full review. The findings will be disseminated through curricular renewal, scientific articles, presentations at international conferences and through social media and popular press. This includes establishing a set of curricular materials for adaptive use that can be made available upon request.

STRENGTHS AND LIMITATIONS

1. A strength of the study is the longitudinal scope, from the development of the workshop content up to an evaluation of learning outcomes and impact. To our knowledge, this is the first study of this type, and it fills a critical gap around the provision and evaluation of education on how to handle microaggressions in academic clinical environments.
2. A limitation of this study is the influence of self-selection bias. Workshop participants volunteered their participation for this program and had the capacity to attend this program. Study participants volunteered to participate in an interview exploring the impact of the workshop on their actions and attitudes.

INTRODUCTION

Designing faculty development focused on equity, diversity, inclusivity, and Indigenous reconciliation (EDI-IR); antiracism; and anti-oppression, is a daunting task [1-3]. In addition, in the Canadian context, health professions educators are called upon to provide skills-based training in anti-racism as one of the 94 Calls to Action by the Truth and Reconciliation Commission of Canada, to alleviate the disproportionate burden of poor health outcome of Indigenous populations [4].

While a didactic approach to continuing professional development in the topics of EDI-IR remains the default at most academic and healthcare institutions, a passive education intervention does not help faculty navigate the high level of tension and emotional labor required to engage with anti-oppressive practices. A disconnect exists between the workshop/presentation environment and the “real world” environment. Simulation-based education, using actors, can therefore be effective in helping faculty members become better educators [5-7]. However, the literature on simulations to address anti-oppression competencies in postgraduate medical education or faculty development is limited [8-10].

As originally defined by Derald Wing Sue: “racial microaggressions are brief and commonplace daily verbal, behavioral, or environmental indignities, whether intentional or unintentional, that communicate hostile, derogatory, or negative racial slights and insults toward people of color” [11]. In addition to people of color, many marginalized groups experience these subtle and casual put-downs and indignities. Ackerman-Barger et al. outlined that in any given incidence of microaggression, there are usually three perspectives: the source, the recipient, and the bystander(s) [12]. Anyone in the clinical teaching environment, including faculty, staff, learners, patients and family members, could find themselves as the source, or recipient, or bystander, to a microaggression. In social science, bystanders have been recognized to have a significant impact in the phenomenon of bullying; bystanders who act are called “upstanders” [13]. The Creating Brave Spaces (CBS) workshop was designed to equip faculty members to disarm microaggressions as an upstander.

In this article, we describe the CBS workshop project in two phases: workshop development and facilitation (Phase 1), and qualitative program evaluation study using realist framework (Phase 2).

METHODS AND ANALYSES

phase 1: workshop development and facilitation

In 2019, McMaster University identified institutional strategic pillars for inclusive excellence (Figure 1). One of the four pillars centers on creating academic content for inclusive excellence. In 2021, a team of volunteers came together to form the Creating Brave Spaces (CBS) team and develop the CBS workshops. On this team, we have clinical faculty, education scientists and administrative staff members. Together, we created two simulation cases, one related to gender-neutral pronouns and the other related to the recognition of Indigenous peoples (see Table 1). The team incorporated best practices for simulation-based education, including separate pre-brief and debriefs for participants and facilitators [14]. We also ensured that participants maintained their personal clinical or academic roles and identities throughout while actors were trained to be

the primary source of the microaggression. Each workshop began with clearly stated learning objectives: 1) identify a microaggression, and 2) gain one technique to disarm microaggressions compassionately.

Figure 1. McMaster’s Four-Pillar EDI Framework. The CBS workshop addresses the pillar in academic content and context. Accessed at [EDI Framework - Four Pillars - Equity and Inclusion Office \(mcmaster.ca\)](https://www.mcmaster.ca/edi/framework) on Feb 28th.

While CBS workshop format and content has evolved over time, there remain some consistent elements. First workshops are led by a team of 3 or 4 co-facilitators. Second a CBS workshop starts by defining the harmful impacts of microaggressions. Facilitators provide some examples of microaggressions experienced in the clinical teaching environment, and introduced the ARISE

acronym (A = Awareness, R = Respond with Empathy, I = Inquiry, S = Statements with “I,” E = Education and Engage) [12]. Using this acronym, we encourage participants to hold the source accountable while remaining curious and compassionate.

Case	Writing and review process	Case synopsis
Gender Neutral Pronouns	The author is a university staff member and a trans woman. She wrote the case based on conversations she overheard in her workplace. The case was then reviewed by the Creating Brave Spaces team and edited into a workshop format.	In a curricular meeting, a senior faculty member experiencing burnout rants about the workload related to changing all pronouns in the teaching cases catalogue to the gender-neutral “they/them.” A workshop facilitator acts as the chair and participants begin as if reviewing the meeting agenda.
Orange Shirt Day Fatigue	The idea came from a faculty member who is an Indigenous woman. She suggested the case idea based on her personal experience. The case was written by a Creating Brave Spaces team member to fit into a workshop format and returned back to the faculty member for review and approval prior to implementation.	In a curricular meeting, a senior clinical leader experiencing burnout rants about having to attend an Orange Shirt Day ceremony in place of other planned commitments that they perceive to be more important.

Table 1. Case writing notes and synopsis.

Third, as part of the pre-brief, facilitators pair each case synopsis (see Table 1) with some context. For example, the case on gender neutral pronouns is paired with data depicting the high level of discomfort that people still have with the concept of communicating in a way that is respectful of people’s gender identities. The scenario is set in a committee meeting context, where all participants, workshop facilitators, and the actor are attending a virtual or in-person curricular meeting. Fourth, only the actor commits a verbal microaggression. The goal is to provoke a response; therefore, if participants react with prolonged silence, the actor’s verbal microaggressions would intensify. The actors are trained to respond defensively if criticized harshly but would retreat if participants deploy any technique to compassionately disarm the actor.

Fifth, within the workshop, facilitators guide participants through rapid cycle deliberate practice [14]. This technique offers flexibility based on the participants’ reaction. The facilitator pauses the scenario, shares observations, prepares the participants for a re-run, or re-run the case until the participants feel comfortable in interrupting and disarming microaggressions. Finally, in the post-workshop debrief, facilitators invite participants to share reactions and analyses of the experience [15]. Facilitators also schedule time to debrief amongst themselves to identify areas that could be improved.

Although the team engages in routine quality improvement, refining workshop format and content through consultation, this research study is conducted with workshop participants recruited in 2023. At this time, a total of 136 faculty members from both inside and external to McMaster University were involved in workshops that were arranged in different settings, including faculty development events, faculty retreats, national and international conferences. The workshops were based on two cases centered in gender diversity and Indigenous reconciliation delivered in both in-person and virtual formats. From each workshop the team gained insight and experience that they incorporate into additional deliveries. Figure 2 presents a summary of “Lessons Learned.” A detailed discussion of these reflections has been published previously [16].

Figure 2. Lessons learned from early experiences in facilitating CBS workshops. This figure was originally published in Tong et al [16].

While we are conducting this research study, the CBS team continues to design new workshops. We look forward to leveraging the findings of the research project towards future workshops.

phase 2: qualitative program evaluation study using realist framework

After having developed and facilitated two cases, we turned our attention to Phase 2 of the project while sourcing and producing additional cases. Studying the effect of EDI-IR faculty development is inherently complex and non-linear. We anticipate that the educational outcome will be heterogenous based on each participants' prior experience, positionality, and current

environment. Sociologists Ray Pawson and Nick Tilley developed the realist evaluation framework to explore the underlying processes by which programs may achieve their outcomes, beyond the binary question of whether an intervention “works” [17]. The realist evaluation asks: “What kinds of educational interventions will tend to work, for what kinds of learners, in what kinds of contexts, to what degree, and what explains such patterns?” [18] The answers to these questions would be formulated as “program theories” in the context-mechanism-outcome format.

In our project, we are in the process of conducting the realist evaluation process with the following steps.

1. Development of interview guide

The planning team and facilitators met to reflect on the intended and actual learning outcomes of the CBS workshops. Through these conversations, the team developed a semi-structured interview guide. The questions were written to prompt participants to reflect on their learning outcomes and possible mechanisms that may facilitate or hinder the application of their learning in their professional context. The questions were structured in such a way that allowed themes to be developed inductively through the data analysis, with a view to generating program theories during analysis. The interview guide also included direct questions where appropriate. For example, we asked about the professional background of each participant, and whether they have any personal experience with prejudice. We asked them to recall their emotions and thoughts during the simulation, their recollection of how the interactions went. We asked them to share their own assessment of whether their knowledge, skills and attitude were impacted through this experience.

2. Pilot interviews and interview guide iteration

Two workshop participants were recruited to pilot the interview guide. The interviewer was a trained research assistant (SC). The transcripts were produced by a professional transcription service. The transcripts of the two pilot interviews were verified against the original audio recording to ensure accuracy. Transcripts were reviewed and discussed further by the team. As a result of the conversation, the interview guide was further modified to gain greater insight into elements of context, mechanism, and outcome. All team meetings where study design modification took place were recorded and transcribed. The meeting transcripts were archived to serve as part of the data set during data analysis.

3. Participant interviews

Seven more participants were recruited after additional runs of the workshops. Transcripts of each interview were produced and archived for analysis. Some interviews were conducted by a second interviewer (XCT).

4. Faculty focus groups

CBS team members, as well as trained standardized actors who performed during simulations, were interviewed in a focus group format to gain additional experiences and verify or build on

the recollection of participants from transcripts. The focus group included two non-CBS team members who had assisted with the facilitation of one online workshop. These conversations added new dimensions and richness to the dataset.

5. Transcript Thematic Analysis

Data analysis was conducted using thematic analysis as described by Braun and Clarke [19]. Participant transcripts were reviewed by all team members in an open format, where notes were placed as comments attached to participants' statements. Subsequently, two team members (XCT, SM) reviewed each transcript iteratively, reading and re-reading, to generate codes in a systematic fashion across the data set, taking care to give equal attention to potential data items. Codes were noted on Post-it notes (© 3M 2024) initially then collected into an Excel (© Microsoft 2024) document, where all relevant extracts for all codes had been collated. The codes that centered around the same ideas were then collated into potential themes. The themes were reviewed and appraised with another review of the entire dataset. While verifying the accuracy of the themes, additional codes that were missed in the first reviews were added to the codebook. Preliminary analysis results were presented to the rest of the study team for additional verification.

We categorized the responses roughly as context and outcome based on the participants answers. On the other hand, the mechanism (of context-mechanism-outcome statements that align with a Realist Evaluation Framework) had to be inferred and theorized through the participants' recollections of their experiences during the workshop, and their connections made between their personal experiences and their own reflections on the impact of the workshop.

6. Member Checking

At this time, we will share the preliminary findings to CBS study team members (SC, HJ, AGS and MS) in a narrated video format. Team members will be asked to consider if the proposed themes align with their observations and experiences as a facilitator. We will also design an online survey tool to bring the research results back to the research participants for additional member checking. When appropriate, transcripts from team meetings and additional participant interactions will be collected for project record.

7. Iteration

In the case that participants do not fully confirm the program theories as generated, we have the flexibility in the project to accommodate additional data collection and necessary analysis as a result, to further refine program theories.

Generally, there is no agreed upon sample size for a qualitative study. Depending on the nature of the research question and the insight of participants, a level of sufficiency can be reached with the data set generated by a small number of participants. The study team is committed to continue data collection as long as new insights relevant to the evaluation can be developed from our interviews, and within the constraints of our resources.

LIMITATIONS

CBS workshop participation is not mandatory. Participants in the research study voluntarily attended. Although the workshops are funded by an internal grant, depending on the organizational structure of each team or individual faculty member, many faculty members are unable to access the program due to competing professional demands; as such, research participation may not represent a full spectrum of target faculty members. Of all workshop participants, a small percentage volunteered to take part in the research study. As such the study participant group may be vulnerable to selection bias, as well as the small sample size.

Participants shared changed attitude, knowledge, and even reported incidences of successfully disarming microaggressions in real life scenarios after the workshop. We recognize that the dataset is vulnerable to recall bias and social desirability bias. However, considering that most workshop participants actively engaged with the simulation during the workshop, and demonstrated their skills in session, we find their responses believable.

ETHICS AND DISSEMINATION

The study proposal was reviewed by the Hamilton Integrated Research Ethics Board. In September 2022, it was determined to fall within quality improvement/program evaluation, and as such was granted a waiver from a full review.

The findings will be disseminated through curricular renewal scientific articles presentations at international conferences and through social media and popular press. This includes establishing a set of curricular materials for adaptive use that is made available to any higher institution teams where this could be valuable, upon request. The curricular materials will include simulation case files, video prompts for virtual workshops, debrief and facilitator guides, reference articles, and a typical workshop agenda. Within McMaster University, the CBS team will leverage our findings to inform future curricular and case development, as well as actor and facilitator training. This collective expertise will be incorporated into future workshop deliveries at conferences and benefit other health professions faculty members in similar contexts.

CONCLUSION

The CBS workshop is a grassroots, customizable, versatile, and efficient educational offering directly addressing microaggressions in the health professions education learning environment. For a limited time, this program is supported by peer-reviewed internal (i.e., institutional) education grants. These grants have been integral to offset the cost of creative work and the use of actors and multiple facilitators, as well as the emotional labor related to facilitating equity work. Although it is clearly aligned with institutional strategic priorities, the workshop has yet to secure long term institutional commitment, as the institution is still in the early stages of formulating a comprehensive EDI-IR curriculum for faculty members. It is our hope to generate early evidence to advocate for the continued support of this kind of innovative learning activities to benefit health professions education faculty members, learners, staff and patients.

CONTRIBUTORSHIP STATEMENT

Dr. Tong is the guarantor for the overall content of the study. She led the Creating Brave Spaces curricular team in the design and implementation, funding acquisition, as well as the writing and editing of the manuscript.

Ms. Chopra contributed to project administration, funding acquisition, data curation and analysis, and review and editing of the manuscript.

Ms. Jordan contributed to the design and implementation of the Creating Brave Spaces curriculum, project administration, funding acquisition, data curation, analysis, and review and editing of the manuscript.

Dr. Sibbald contributed to funding acquisition, data curation and analysis, and review and editing of the manuscript.

Mr. Geekie-Sousa contributed to the design and implementation of the Creating Brave Spaces curriculum, as well as the review and editing of the manuscript.

Dr. Monteiro contributed to funding acquisition, data curation and analysis, and review and editing of the manuscript.

Drs. Anita Acai, Renate Kahlke, Teresa Chan, and Lara Varpio consulted on the methodology of the study throughout the process.

Drs. Saroo Sharda, Associate Dean of Equity and Inclusivity, and Dr. Ruth Chen, Acting Associate Dean of Continuing Professional Development, lent institutional support to the CBS project in 2024.

Dr. Suzanne Archie, Dr. Patricia Farrugia, Renata Hall, Lisa Jeffs and Oliver Thorne contributed to the content development and delivery of CBS workshops as lead facilitators in 2024.

Dr. Arden Azim, Ms. Pamela Elmhirst, Drs. Patricia Farrugia, Anjali Kundi, Tejal Patel, Saroo Sharda, Madeleine Verhovsek and Mohammad Zubairi contributed to the design and delivery of CBS workshops in 2021-2023.

The CBS team appreciates the talent of Michael G. DeGroot School of Medicine Waterloo Regional Campus standardized actors, in particular Dan Sanderson and Raymond Louter, for their dedication and nuanced performance.

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The CBS team is currently (2024) supported by the McMaster Gender and Health Grant to continue designing and delivering Creating Brave Spaces workshops while the study team completes final data analysis.

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